

PERSONAL INFORMATION

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SCENARIO

Title: Authorship Deserved, Not Earned: Research Ethics and Research Integrity Scenario

Research area discussed in the scenario: Authorship manipulation

ECCRI contexts discussed in the scenario: Publication and dissemination; Research environment

Narrative:

Allan is a recent graduate in biomedicine at the beginning of his career. Following graduation, he was offered a temporary position as a laboratory technician at the Department of Physiology of a University, where he conducted his master thesis. Although Allan originally had a PhD position or a job in the biomedical industry in mind, he accepted the job offer, but continued searching for other options. The Head of Department promised Allan a PhD in his group once funding has been secured, as "Allan would be an asset to their team". Meanwhile, Allan continues applying for other positions, unsuccessfully, as most PhD advertisements demand a candidate to already have a publication, which Allan did not have, alongside a list of academic references.

His scope of work as a lab technician includes working on the Department's research projects in terms of performing animal experiments and other laboratory experimental work. PhD students and postdocs are in charge of data analysis and interpretation for publications. For one project in particular, besides experimental procedures, Allan was asked to also analyze a dataset, as he has had previous experience with the analysis in question. These results are going to be included in a manuscript, planned to be sent to a high-impact journal. A scientific publication in Allan's CV would make him an attractive candidate for a PhD position elsewhere. Allan asks the Head of the Department (who is the principal investigator on this project) whether he would be included in the paper as a co-author, the Head responds that he was employed as a lab technician, not a PhD student, and that his primary duties were to provide technical support to the scientists. Allan raises an argument that he also participated in data analysis and hence should be offered to participate in revising the manuscript draft, which would make him eligible for authorship according to authorship criteria of the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE). The Department Head reminds him that

the fixed-term lab technician position was opened specifically for him while they are awaiting for a PhD grant, that it is his time to prove himself worthy of such a favor, and “once he is a PhD student they can discuss authorship criteria.”

Allan is angry and confused, and begins rethinking his options. If he continues fighting for his right to authorship, he might win, but also provoke retaliation from the Department’s Head. He casually mentions his concerns to Mike, an ex-colleague who was previously employed as a postdoc in the lab, but recently left to work for a large pharmaceutical company. Apparently, this is not the first occasion when the Head decided on the authorship according to his very own criteria, with disregard for common and accepted research community practices. At one occasion, the Head's good friend and a colleague needed an extra publication for his tenure application, so he was serendipitously added to the list of co-authors, as he “made his contribution by giving an idea for a part of the research, whatever that idea was”, according to Mike. “Every one of us had to go through this. Those are the game rules in this lab... It's best you just bite this bullet and keep your head down if you want to get that PhD, or a reference for later. I definitely would not be working where I am now if the Head did not call a few old acquaintances to put in a good word for me,” Mike responds indifferently.

However, unwilling to let go of the opportunity to have his work recognized, Allan politely but assertively makes up his case to the Head once again, who angrily rejects his request with a threat that “his attitude will abridge him of a positive reference for any future job he wants to take”. This leaves Allan with different options for further action. He can stay and let the dust settle, continue diligently performing his work and wait for a PhD opening in the current lab or elsewhere, well aware he is in need of a good recommendation letter. On the other hand, the idea about quitting and reporting the Head to the authorities seems appealing and righteous, but his institution does not have a research integrity office, and the University's research ethics committee is infamous for long response time and having a lot of bureaucracy in their proceedings.

Keywords: authorship; misconduct; hiring and promotion practice; research integrity; mentor/trainee relationship

References:

1. ICMJE | Recommendations | Defining the Role of Authors and Contributors [Internet]. Icmje.org. 2021 [cited 11 October 2021]. Available from: <http://www.icmje.org/recommendations/browse/roles-and-responsibilities/defining-the-role-of-authors-and-contributors.html#twoICMJE>

Suggestions for further readings:

The Office of Research Integrity: [Publications/Authorship](#)

COPE: [How to handle authorship disputes: a guide for new researchers](#)

ALLEA: [The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#)

UKRIO: [Good practice in research: Authorship](#)

QUESTIONS

Questions for researchers:

1. Department of Physiology will be opening a PhD position, which Allan considers a contingency plan if he fails to find other placements. Should he adhere to the rules set by the Head of Department and let go of the authorship dispute, and hence a publication needed for a PhD application elsewhere? A good relationship with the Head would benefit him in terms of ensuring a recommendation letter. On the other hand, by accepting the given terms, would Allan also participate in unethical behavior?
2. Would you accept employment in a lab that nurtures employment practices as described in a scenario, i.e. having pre-arranged employments, but at the same time restraining young researchers from making progress at the beginning of their career through ghost-authoring publications?

Questions for research administrators:

1. What can be done to increase the awareness of and adherence to responsible practices in authorship in your institution?
2. How can researchers communicate their concerns about irresponsible research practices to the administration?

Questions for research ethics committees and research integrity offices:

1. Allan performed experimental procedures and analyses but has not participated in drafting the manuscript, as it was not offered to him, which does not make him eligible for authorship according to the ICMJE criteria (although ICMJE criteria emphasize that those contributing to research should be offered to contribute to writing up of a manuscript). How can Allan present his case to the authorities, so he has a firm ground to stand on, without being too emotional and appearing to seek vengeance?

2. If a third person that would perhaps find out about ghost and gift authorship misconduct blows the whistle on the Head, would Allan and the rest of the group be responsible for negligence to report?